

Arguments for Habilitation 2.0

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

Running title: Arguments for Habilitation 2.0

Keywords: habilitation

DRAFT
#gasocrine

Abstract

In several countries, habilitation is a prestigious title awarded to the most accomplished experts in the field, recognizing their scientific or artistic achievements. If the habilitation process in biology-related academic research were perfect, and all past habitations on oxygen (O₂)-sensing, hypoxia and oxidative stress were well-deserved, why have so few researchers asked fundamental questions like: If there is a receptor for NO (nitric oxide), is there a receptor for O₂? Or, if there is an O₂ receptor in bacteria, is there an O₂ receptor in other organisms such as mice or humans? The 1998 Nobel Prize in Physiology and medicine highlighted the receptor for NO, and publications from the 1990s already reported O₂-sensing proteins like DosP or FixL in bacteria. With over half a million publications on hypoxia or oxidative stress by 2024, we still do not know the identity of human O₂-sensing receptors or gasoreceptors. What does this say about all the past successful habitations in hypoxia or oxidative stress research presented after the first O₂-sensing protein and NO receptor were published? Does this indicate a flaw in the habilitation system? Or do all the habitations related to oxidative stress and hypoxia research have nothing to do with O₂-sensing gasoreceptors? If it is a flaw, then what has to be changed in the current habilitation evaluation criteria?

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Savani Anbalagan: conceptualization, writing of the original draft, and review and editing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

S.A. is supported by National Science Centre grants (SONATA-BIS 2020/38/E/NZ3/00090 and SONATA 2021/43/D/NZ3/01798).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

The funding agency and institution S.A. is affiliated with was not involved in the contents of the manuscript.

DRAFT
#gasocrine